

SHORT NOTES

Structure of 3-Hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene

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3-Hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene has been recently reported¹ as a highly selective reagent for palladium and copper. The metallic complexes are insoluble in water, soluble in organic solvents, thermally stable, of definite composition, and suitable for direct weighing. These can be crystallised from acetone and exhibit sharp melting points.

The UV absorption spectrum of 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene was taken with a Beckman quartz spectrophotometer, model DU. It shows two absorption maxima at 238 and 348 m μ . There was no change in the absorption maxima of solutions prepared between pH 1.0 and 6.0. In alkaline medium, the absorption maximum at 348m μ shifts to 390m μ . The following equilibrium possibly exists:

This change in absorption maximum with pH has been used in determining its acid dissociation constant by employing Robinson's spectrophotometric method². The pK value has been determined³ as 11.41.

On the general background of chemistry, 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene is expected to be a stronger acid than phenol. The expected acid character may be attributed to the resonance stabilisation of the anion (IV).

Structures (V to X) indicate that the negative charge on the anion is distributed over two benzene rings. Hence we should expect the ready loss of a proton from hydroxytriazene than from phenol. The high pK value 11.41 of 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene provides just the opposite picture. The suppression of the acid character may possibly

1. Sogani and Bhattacharya, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, **28**, 81; 1956, **28**, 1616.

2. Robinson, Abs. Symp., "Structure of Electrolytic Solutions", Washington, 1957, p. 90.

3. Purohit, Ph. D. Thesis, 1963, University of Rajasthan.

be due to its existence in intramolecular hydrogen bonded form (XI) and its tautomeric form (XII).

By an analogy with the structure assigned to its metallic complexes, Elkins and Hunter⁴ have suggested the hydrogen-bonded structure, where the proton is liberated by a metal ion in complex formation. This structure is supported by UV absorption studies in acid medium. There is no indication of attachment of proton to either of the nitrogen atoms 1 and 2. This could only happen when a structure involving attachment of hydrogen through hydrogen bonding is already existing. This structure is further supported by the ready solubility in hydrocarbon solvents and low melting point (120°) of the triazene.

The I R absorption spectrum of 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene has an absorption band at 3190 cm^{-1} , which is indicative of hydrogen bonding. Similar stretching of -OH group in intramolecular hydrogen bonding of oximes⁵, corresponding to absorption bands

4. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1340.

5. Flett, "Physical Aids to the Organic Chemist", Elsevier Publishing Co., 1962, p. 178.

between 3100 and 3250 cm^{-1} , is known. If the intramolecular hydrogen-bonded structure of 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene is correct, then it should have *trans* configuration and that all the nuclei are in the same plane.

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